

IFLA Regional Division
Committee
Middle East
and North Africa

جامعة الأنخوين
AL AKHAWAYN
UNIVERSITY

MOHAMMED VI LIBRARY

Towards Sustainable Development in Academic Libraries: The case of Mohammed VI Library at AUI

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OUTLINE

1. Introducing Al Akhawayn University in Ifrane and the Mohammed VI Library
2. Al Akhawayn University's Strategic Plan (2020-2025)
3. AUI's contribution to the UN SDGs
4. M6L's contribution to the UN SDGs
5. Future actions towards achieving SDGs

Al Akhawayn University in Ifrane (AUI)

- Founded in 1993 by Royal Dahir; officially opened in January 1995
- A liberal arts institution modeled on the American university system
- Curricula divided into three main schools:
 - School of Humanities & Social Sciences
 - School of Business Administration
 - School of Science & Engineering
 - & Language Center

Mohammed VI Library (M6L)

- AUI's university library;
- Supports learning, teaching and research;
- Committed to information literacy and creative endeavors in a welcoming environment

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AUI's contribution to the UN
SDGs

AUI's Mission

"AUI is committed to educating future citizen-leaders of Morocco and the world through a globally oriented, English language, Liberal Arts curriculum based on the American system. The University enhances Morocco and engages the world through leading-edge educational and impact research programs, including continuing and executive education, upholds the highest academic and ethical standards, and promotes equity and social responsibility."

-AUI's Strategic Plan 2020-2025

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AUI's Strategic Plan (2020- 2025)

- **Pillar 6: Financial, Environmental, & Institutional Exemplarity & Sustainability**
- ***Sub-Pillar 6. AUI Contribution to UN Sustainable Development Goals***
- ✓ Creation of new initiatives supporting the region in implementation of and commitment to UN Sustainability Goals
- ✓ 6.E.1 Quality education: Accreditation and scholarships for eligible students
- ✓ 6.E.2 No poverty: Support & expand the work of Azrou center
- ✓ 6.E.3 Zero hunger: Enhance the activities of Hand in Hand and charitable activities
- ✓ 6.E.4 Affordable & clean energy: Reduce carbon footprint
- ✓ 6.E.5 Gender equality: Increase female diversity
- ✓ 6.E.6 Good health & wellbeing: Expand coverage of medical caravan

(AUI Strategic Plan 2020-2025)

No poverty

1 NO
POVERTY

“AUI has organized a set of events and initiatives to help with the no poverty SDG and they are as follows:

- Monitoring of clubs : Al Akhawayn donated 250 food baskets of food for the population in the Imlil region.
- Establishment of a Azrou center : organized a donation of 100 food baskets food in the region of Tigrigra.”

No hunger

“During last year, two main initiatives were done by clubs of AUI to fight the hunger in the rural areas and they are as follows

- Lions Club Al Akhawayn donated 250 baskets of food for the population in the Imlil region.
- Hand in Hand club organized a donation of 100 baskets of food in the region of Tigrira.”

Good health and well being

“AUI provides medical services to Ifrane's region population through organizing several types of actions :

- Medical campaigns
- Diabetese awareness
- Blood donations
- Circumcision ”

Quality Education

Constantly improving its programs to fit the job market and the needs of the students.

×A set of accreditations for its different school and programs which are

Clubs try to develop the education within the region through both a tutoring program and school backpacks donation to insure the best study conditions for those students.

4 QUALITY EDUCATION

Computing &
Engineering
Accreditation
Commissions

Gender Equality

- 52.98% of female students and 47.02% of male students.
- 60 female professor and 144 male professor.
- 1126 residency beds for females and 1376 bed for males.
- 2 female deans were recently appointed in both SBA and SHSS schools.

Affordable and Clean Energy

- AUI is using PV panels to support its energy independency.

Climate Action

School of Science and Engineering

- The **Master** of Science in Sustainable Energy Management program
- AUI participation in Renewable Energy-based E-Mobility in Higher Education (REMO).

M6L's contribution to the UN SDGs

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MOHAMMED VI LIBRARY

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- Lending books services
 - Extended library opening hours during midterm and final exams period
 - Providing access to a revised and updated collection of print and electronic resources that meet the needs of the community, on and off-campus.
 - Information and digital Literacy workshops

- A collection of resources on women's studies.
- Organized a book exhibition on Domestic Violence
- M6L Speaker series (Gender & Sexuality in Morocco; A New Protest Culture: Rise of Fourth Wave Feminism in Morocco)

-
- Cost-effective methods to ensure efficient energy use (weatherproofing, door and window repairs)
 - Provides access to a multitude of resources on clean & renewable energy

- High speed internet
- Digital humanities bootcamp
- Student-led cross institutional collaboration between Al Akhawayn and The American University of Paris in Fall 2022
- M6L speaker series (Empowering healthcare through data analytics & Artificial Intelligence, Digital Futures for the Humanities)

9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION
AND INFRASTRUCTURE

- M6L Digital Repository to showcase and preserve documents of durable historical value
- Open-source platform
- Preservation of local cultural heritage

- Recycled part of the printed collection and disposed of the materials in various sustainable ways:
 - Donations (lycée d'Azrou)
 - Book sales
 - Partnership with SOREPAC to recycle tons of accumulated paper waste

12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

- Transformed spaces using already existing furniture
 - M6L Café Space Area
 - Group and individual study rooms
 - M6L Think space
 - Mezzanine Study Area

2021

2022

2022

Future actions towards achieving SDGs

Incorporate the SDGs clearly into the library's strategic plan

Outreach to faculty members and other campus partners to develop collaborative projects on the theme of Sustainable Development

Create a research guide on sustainable development and the SDGs

Pursue solar energy plan

Promote open scholarship : open access, open data, OERs

Professional Development for librarians on the topic of sustainable development and green libraries

Works Cited

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The background consists of a dense, overlapping collage of colorful sticky notes in shades of teal, purple, green, and yellow. Each sticky note features a large, black, hand-drawn question mark. A white rectangular border is centered on the page, framing the main text.

QUESTIONS?

Thank You!